

TRADITIONAL POLICING AGENTS AND CRIME CONTROL: AN ASSESSMENT OF USEH IDUNG IN MKPAT ENIN LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA

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ABSTRACT

This research work examined the Roles of Useh Idung as Traditional Policing Agents in Controlling Criminal Activities in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The research made use of Emile Durkheim theory of Policing as a framework. Ethnographic research design was adopted by the researcher for the study. The sample for this study were youths aged between 15 and 50 years, who were randomly selected through the big-net approach from the four clans across the local government area. After deciding on what and who to study, the researcher adopted the Fatterman's big-net approach for sample size, interview was the major method of data collection. Findings of the study were analysed qualitatively in thematic analysis with excerpts (verbatim reports) from emic responses of the people. Findings of the study revealed that Useh Idung is a network of Iwaad and Mkpawara in crime control and prevention across the villages in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. It was recommended that government should empower community traditional policing agents like Useh Idung for effective collaboration with the Nigerian Police Force toward more effective crime prevention in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

KEYWORDS: Traditional Policing Agents, Crime Control, Useh Idung and Mkpato Enin

INTRODUCTION

People have become interested in crime because it is a social problem; it is like an epidemic disease that attacks the rights of individuals and groups, and it is a universal phenomenon and it differs only in degree amongst the various nations of the world (Femi *et al*, 2015). Esiri (2016) posits that crime has generated a hot debate in the agenda of most nations, yet it does not seem to be on the decline, rather it is on the increase. According to Esiri (2016), crime rates are much higher in cities than in rural areas and this has been the trend for several

centuries. Crime is one of the human security problems confronting humanity across the world, nations have grappled to contain the rising incidence of homicide, armed robbery, and kidnapping, drug trafficking, sex trafficking, illegal gun running and host of others (Nwankwo and James, 2016). United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime in 2011 reported that homicides globally were estimated at 468,000 and more than a third (36%) was estimated to have occurred in Africa, 31% in the Americas, 27% in Asia, 5% in Europe and 1% in the tropical Pacific region (Nwankwo and James, 2016).

Africa has remained a leading continent in global crime statistics and the prevalence of violent and non-violent crimes has remained high in South Africa and Nigeria (Nwankwo, and James, 2016). According to Africa Check, incidents of murder increased from 15 609 murders in 2011/12 to 16 259 murders in 2012/13 in South Africa, with an increase of 650 murder cases or a 4, 2% increase when comparing the total numbers of murders with the previous year (Nwankwo and James, 2016). The same source also reported that murders and attempted murders that took place in South Africa during an aggravated robbery or inter-group conflict (such as gang or taxi violence), and vigilantism makeup between 35% and 45% of all murders and attempted murders (Nwankwo and James, 2016). According to Nwankwo and James, (2016), the story remains the same in Nigeria which has been hit by several forms of crimes.

There is no universal definition of crime, and this is a result of changes in social, political, psychological and economic conditions (Femi *et al*, 2015). The definition or conception of crime is based on offences being committed against the citizens of a country or its sets of rule and regulations (Omoyibo, 2012). The value system of a society defines what is criminal and as a result, the rate, type, cause, and effect on each society or community may differ widely (Esiri, 2016). Crime has been defined in various ways Marshall and Clark (1952) cited in Esiri, (2016), defined crime as “any act or omission prohibited by public law for the protection of the public and punishable by state in a judicial proceeding in its name.” Tappan (1960) cited in Esiri (2016) defined crime as “an instrumental act or omission in violation of criminal law, committed without justification and sanctioned by the state as felony or misdemeanor.” Again, Clinard (1974) cited in Esiri (2016) wrote that crime refers to those activities which break the law of the land and are subject to official punishment after conviction. Crime is now a global phenomenon to which all towns and cities are susceptible (Kinsella, 2012).

Police and policing are words that are known and used by all classes and categories of age cohorts around the world. The word police was coined from the Greek words politeuein, which means to be a citizen or engage in political activity, and polis, which means a city or state (Roberg, Crank and Kuykendall, 2000 cited in Johnson 2013). Police as a relative term to the Greek words is positioned to carry out the functions of law enforcement, order maintenance, service and gather information within the state or community. This implies that, the police are the major representatives of the legal system in their transactions with citizens of the state or community (Johnson, 2013). Newburn (2004) posits that policing and police work did not start as a paid profession; rather, it started as a noble, incorruptible profession with considerable responsibility and distinction.

Police are viewed under the traditional policing model as the primary guardians of safety of the society with primary responsibilities of responding to reported and observed crimes, conduct investigations, identify suspects, and make arrests accordingly (US

Department of Justice, 2010). Traditional methods of community policing has long been employed in Africa before the arrival of the Europeans, to curb, control and prevent crimes at various level or among different age groups. Policing in the African context started with the traditional policing agents within the traditional cultural setting of the traditional society. Despite the modern trends of policing, effective community policing most especially in African countries is still a phenomenon that combines the African traditional policing systems with Europeans policing systems for effective delivery of crimes control. Ayuk, Owan and Uyang (2013) opined that traditional methods of controlling crime and maintaining security is culturally relative and not of universal acceptance. Community policing or neighbourhood policing or proximity policing are the same in context but has been variously defined (Aniche, 2016). Community policing entails community partnership in creating a safe and secure environment for all in which people take active part in their own affairs (Ikuteyijo and Rotimi, 2012).

Crime is at alarming rate in Nigeria, and there are many factors that are contributing to this anti-societal behaviour both among the youths and adults in our society today (Femi *et al.*, 2015). Alcohol and drugs are key influential factors of deviant behaviour among youths in Nigeria (Peters, 2019; Peters, Basse, and Usoro, 2020; Peters and Basse, 2020; Peters, Basse, Usoro, and Samuel, 2022; Peters, Usoro, James, Emeh, and Oyebanji, 2023 and Peters, Usoro, Mboho, and Ononokpono, 2023). Basse and Peters (2021) revealed that parental guidance is a contributing factor to young people anti-social behaviour. Traditional institution plays great role in the control of youths' activities especially in the rural areas (Peters and Basse, 2019). Crime manifest in the convulsive upsurge of both violent and non-violent crimes (Nwankwo and James, 2016). Incidents of armed robbery, assassination and ransom-driven kidnapping are now ravaging the polity like a tsunami and spreading a climate of fears and anxieties about public safety. The upsurge of crime has been ongoing as Nigeria has been on the global crime map since 1980s. The challenge of coping with the policing of the Nigerian society is much more as compared to what it was in the early days of the nation thereby creating the position for the police and community partnership toward achieving effective policing.

Though crime is a global phenomenon with every society facing its bit of heat, Akwa Ibom State was viewed with dignity by the forebears, who frowned at criminal activities and ensured that perpetrators of violent crime were severely punished and often times their punishments were extended to their immediate close relatives. In the traditional Akwa Ibom community, criminals were never allowed to be at peace with themselves, which made their survival among the people a difficult one, and in most cases, criminals had to flee their communities to avoid shame in order to save their lives. Taboos were used to check human behaviours against going beyond the moral external boundary of the community. Crime and criminal activities were forbidden and families were ashamed of having children who are known or noted to engage in crimes or criminal activities.

In recent times, Akwa Ibom State has witnessed a rise in crimes and criminal activities within the communities as a behavioural shift from the urban areas to the rural communities and as impact of globalization through the use of technology. This scenario has influence the dynamic character of culture, thereby bringing about cultural shift from what was forbidden to what is gradually becoming a new way of life in various rural communities. The urban centres

in Akwa Ibom State have witnessed various criminal activities. These criminal activities range from kidnapping, arm robbery, burglary, theft, to rape. The criminal situation within the state has been calling for more input by the security agencies, as some rural communities are being invaded by criminal youths; to steal, rape, kill and terrorize people.

The effectiveness of crime prevention especially in most rural communities has been a serious challenge in recent years across our nation. The indecent killing of innocent people across the country by herdsmen, bandits, kidnapers, terrorists, cultist, and what is referred to as unknown gun men have pose great challenge to the effectiveness and efficiency of the policing institution across the country, with the north positioned at the worst receiving ends. The spread of security challenges are those of all societies in Nigeria. This demands effective combinations of all security parties in the quest for peace and safety of lives and properties as a primary right of the citizens.

Literatures have revealed the importance of traditional policing system. According to Aniche (2016), traditional African societies had means of social control, reformation and moral cleanser which served then as instruments to correct and serve justice even before the advent of Western colonization. These means of crime prevention according to Ayuk, Owan, and Uyang, (2013) serves through community settings which like in the Igbo extraction of eastern Nigeria, each lineage system within a community, is made up of a number of territorially kin-based units, which each unit is made up of economically independent households and each household recognized the authority of the compound head, and the compound head has numerous rituals, moral and legal rights, and obligation. The head of the family or village offers sacrifices for the welfare of his compound members, whom he helps to extricate from the ritual, social and legal problems. This traditional pattern is similar to Akwa Ibom State traditional cultural setting.

Long before the coming of Europeans, the traditional Igbo society of the now south-eastern Nigeria had devised means of policing its communities and curbing or preventing crime using primarily the age grade system and masquerade secret society (Aniche, 2016). Before the advent of Western civilization and penal system to Africa and indeed Nigeria, traditional African societies had means of social control, reformation and moral cleanser which served then as instruments to correct and serve justice (Ayuk, *et al* 2013). The over dependency on the Nigerian Police Force without proper assimilation of the traditional security agents has brought about security leakages in rural communities. Though some literature have shown the importance of traditional policing system in Nigeria, there exist a gap in the assessment of the various roles of these traditional security agents as a panacea for failing community policing facing many communities in Nigeria today. Based on this backdrop, this research work seeks to assess the roles of Useh Idung as traditional policing agent in crimes control in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Emile Durkheim's Theory of Policing

Jackson and Sunshine (2007) currently used a neo-Durkheimian attitude in the look at public self-belief of the police. According to Jackson and Sunshine, Durkheim proposed that society judges the police following their ability to defend and represent the morals and values of society. Jackson and Sunshine (2007) based on Durkheim's theory of policing posits that

people judge whether the police are representatives of community values and morals. According to scholars, people judged a range of things in their community as hostile to social order, and by linking such symbols of breakdown with the danger of victimisation, human beings used 'crime' as a neo-Durkheimian marker of ethical structure. The fear of crime emerged as a lay seismograph of social organisation and control, expressing and distilling a whole set of evaluative activities.

The application of the theory to the study is in the fact that the study area as a local government area considers that; the police as an institution is a representative of the community which is expected to uphold the moral boundaries of the community and protect lives and properties, while seeking to arrest and work on prosecuting those considered to be deviants or criminals by the community. Therefore, this implies that the community through traditional institutions contributes to the policing of the community.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted ethnographic research design because the study sought to observe and gather information on the roles of traditional policing agents in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. This research design facilitates a search for information to gain insight on the substantial issues in the study because of its exploratory, investigative and explanatory potentials which may be useful for further research study on the different variables as highlighted by the researcher in this study.

This type of research design provides for multiple qualitative data collection techniques and analysis. This made interview schedule a convenient tool for primary data collection in the study. It also facilitates in-depth analysis of the roles of traditional policing agents in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The data collected will be analysed using thematic analysis technique in accordance to gathered information from the field.

Mkpato-Enin is located in the South-South region of Nigeria and is a town and a local government area (LGA) of Akwa Ibom State. It sits at an altitude of approximately 185 metres (607 ft) above sea level. Mkpato Enin Local Government Area has an area of 322.352 square kilometres (124.461 sq mi) and it's the second largest local government area in Akwa Ibom state. The Local Government Area is located within the industrial belt extending from Eastern Obolo, Etinan, Oruk Anam, Onna, to Ikot Abasi. The people are traditionally Ibibio speakers. The population was 178,036 based on the 2006 census. The area is rich in oil and natural gas; oil was discovered in Ikot Akpa/Ekop as early as 1953. Forest reserves in the local government area include timber and palm produce. One of the campuses of the Akwa Ibom State University is located in this community. The local government area has four clans and 87 villages. According to the 2006 population census result, Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State has 178,036 populations (NPC, 2006). By 2019, according to the Akwa Ibom State Demographic Profile (2018), Mkpato Enin Local Government Area had a projected population as calculated based on the 2006 census result indices to stand at 264, 812 of both males and females.

The researcher adopted a big-net approach (Fatterman, 2010) to determine the study sample and gathered information from the study participants. The data for this study were obtained from primary sources through personal in-depth interviews of study participants.

Apart from in-depth interviews, other data collection methods were used in the research. These are participant observation, informal discussion, and participatory appraisal through dialogue with the people of Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The research instrument adopted by the researcher for this study was the interview schedule. The interview schedule was structured with open questions, allowing the respondents to give out information without being controlled or limited to specific responses. Data collected in this study from the interview schedule were analysed thematically using verbatim reports (excerpts) in line with the findings of the study.

RESULT

Roles of Useh Idung in Crime Prevention in Mkpato Enin

Gathered data have shown that Useh Idung is the vigilante group that is responsible for traditional security activities of the various communities in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Through observation and interviews, it was discovered that their activities range from mounting road blocks at night in their respective communities, keeping night watch over their respective communities, investigating crimes, helping in arrest of criminals by the Nigerian Police Force, collaborating with other governmental security agencies to prevent crimes and interception of crimes. Study participants have narrated their views on the important roles played by Useh Idung which make them more preferred to some of the rural people the Mkpato Enin Local Government Area when it comes to crime prevention especially within the rural communities. According to one of the study participants, Useh Idung played more important role in crime prevention than the Nigerian Police. According to her;

These people will not sleep at night as compare to the police who will even park their vehicle and sleep, and these Useh Idung will go into the interior parts of the village and those village roads which these criminals mostly used to mount road block, but the police will only stay at the major roads and junctions and be waiting for calls from Useh Idung and others about criminal acts before the police will later see how to come after. So, to me these Useh Idung are working more than the police when it comes to checking and preventing crime in our villages (female, 39 years, interviewed on 23/11/2023).

Useh Idung have been the security eye of the various communities in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. This group of young people has been responsible for crime prevention in their respective communities through fetching out persons who engage criminal activities within their community. According to narratives during interview, one of the study participants reported that;

This Useh Idung people are working in this village because they are looking for anybody that they hear has done pim... or steal anything in this village. They will fetch you out unless you run away, and when you decide to run away, make sure that you don't come back because they will be waiting to catch you and hand you over to the police. These things they do have really make our

boys to stay calm and forget committing crime. In fact, even if you think about crime, you cannot easily do it (female, 35 years, interviewed on 23/11/2023).

Another participant narrated that;

If you commit crime in this village and think that you can hide, it's a lie because Useh Idung will fetch you out. There was this man you assaulted his wife and ran away to his friend's house in another village. I was surprised that Useh Idung in this village can work with Useh Idung in another village as police to fetch out the man and brought him back to this village and hand him over to the Police (male, 39 years, interviewed on 21/11/2023).

Gathered data revealed that Useh idung in Mkpato Enin local Government Area have been a network of traditional security operative which operate in different communities but work together when it comes to crime prevention as one of their major objectives. Data have revealed that their networking have been in the area of fetching out criminals who tried to run away from their indigenous communities to another community within Mkpato Enin and in investigating, and returning of stolen properties which were stolen and transferred to another community within Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. The partnerships between Useh Idung from different communities in Mkpato Enin have brought about effective result in crime preventions within the local government area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

It was revealed by findings of the study that Useh Idung which is referred in English as “Vigilante group” has been an effective and efficient traditional policing agency in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. This traditional policing group has been made up of both Obong Iwaad who in most villages are the leadership of the Useh Idung, and Obong Mkpawara who in most villages have been responsible for mobilization of youths into Useh Idung for the main aim of crime prevention in Mkpato Enin. Findings of the study also revealed that Useh Idung have been the security eye of the various communities in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. Further findings also revealed that Useh idung in Mkpato Enin local Government Area have been a network of traditional security operative which operate in different communities but work together when it comes to crime prevention as one of their major objectives. It was revealed that their networking have been in the area of fetching out criminals who tried to run away from their indigenous communities to another community within Mkpato Enin and in investigating, and returning of stolen properties which were stolen and transferred to another community within Mkpato Enin Local Government Area. This network according to findings, have brought about effective result in crime preventions within the local government area. These findings agreed with Adebayo (2013) who posits that traditional crime prevention has its roots in kinship, and the extended family network prior to the advent of formal agencies of social control in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Useh Idung, play key roles in the prevention of crimes in Mkpato Enin Local

Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Obong Iwaads have been leaders of vigilante groups; they have led team of community securities to engage in road block in the nights which have enabled them to intercept criminal intended plans and activities thereby engaging in crime preventions. Useh Idung has been a network of both Iwaad and Mkparawa, and their inter-village network has been effective in crime prevention through fetching out criminals who tried to run away from their indigenous communities to another community within Mkpát Enin and in investigating, and returning of stolen properties which were stolen and transferred to another community within Mkpát Enin Local Government Area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Useh Idung should be empowered by the state with necessary equipment and trainings in line with their traditional policing strategies toward more efficient crime prevention.
- ii. Government should empower community traditional policing agent for effective collaboration with the Nigerian Police Force toward more effective crime prevention in Mkpát Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

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